

STRESS AND WORK-FAMILY BALANCE AMONG WOMEN EMPLOYEES OF SELECTED COMMERCIAL BANKS IN LOKOJA METROPOLIS

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Abstract

Work is a crucial aspect of life that provides satisfaction for many individuals, but it can also serve as a significant source of stress. The study therefore examined the stress and work-family balance among women employees of commercial banks in Lokoja metropolis. The specific objectives of the study includes exploring the expectations of work-life balance and policy requirements among women working in the banking industry, identifying the primary sources of stress among women employees working in the banking industry, investigating the challenges related to family responsibilities faced by women in the banking industry, to examine the work-related challenges encountered by women in the banking industry and to analyse the coping strategies adopted by women to manage stress and overcome challenges in both their work and family lives. This study was anchored on Role, Spillover and Work-family Conflict Theories and adopted a combination of self-administered questionnaire and in-depth interview for primary data. Secondary data were obtained through internet documented materials, journals articles and textbooks among others. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting 120 respondents for the study. However, 96 respondents duly completed the questionnaires and which were analyzed using inferential and descriptive statistics. The In-depth interviews results were analyzed using content analysis. The research findings revealed that giving priority to women employees, introducing better policies and paying leave bonuses promptly were expectations about work-life balance and policy requirements in the banking industry. The study revealed also that pressure to meet up with set targets and deadlines; long working hours and excess workload were some of the primary sources of work stress among women employees in the banking industries. The study also revealed that caring for dependents, the need to balance family responsibilities, work commitments and conflict in marriage over managing of family responsibilities were most of the family related challenges faced by women employees in the banking industry. Also, the study revealed that work-related challenges included hostile attitudes from some customers, meeting up with required targets and resumption time. Attending social gatherings, relaxing, engaging in exercise such as swimming, walking are some of the coping strategies among others adopted by women working in commercial banks. The study concluded that women in commercial banks aspire for a work-life balance that accommodates their professional and personal needs, with a focus on flexibility and supportive policies, stress among these women primarily arises from job demands and workplace competition and the findings shed light on the multifaceted challenges faced by women in striving to harmonize their professional aspirations with family responsibilities. Hence, the study recommends that banking industries should prioritize the implementation of flexible work policies and support systems to enable women to better balance their professional and family lives.

KEYWORDS: Work Stress, Women Employees, Work-Family Balance, Commercial Banks, Organizations, Lokoja Metropolis, Nigeria.

Introduction

Work is a crucial aspect of life that provides satisfaction for many individuals, but it can also serve as a significant source of stress. Stress is a prevalent human phenomenon resulting from the complex interaction between life events and an individual's subjective interpretation of those events. It refers to the pressure individuals experience in their lives, which arise from an imbalance between environmental demands and personal capabilities to meet them (Smith, 2022). Work refers to an activity involving mental or physical effort done to achieve a specific purpose or result (Locke & Latham, 2019). It encompasses various tasks, duties, or responsibilities performed by individuals in exchange for compensation or to contribute to the functioning of an organization or society as a whole. Work can take different forms, including paid employment, volunteer activities, or personal projects aimed at achieving goals and fulfilling obligations. Stress refers to the physiological and psychological reactions that individuals undergo when they perceive a situation as challenging or surpassing their capacity to cope (Selye, 2019). It encompasses the intricate interaction between external stressors, such as work demands and life events, and internal cognitive processes, such as perception and interpretation, which shape an individual's response to these stressors.

Balancing work and family life has become a prominent source of stress for working adults in today's productivity-driven society. More and more people are finding it difficult to fulfill their roles effectively both at home and in the workplace (Heissman, 2022). Consequently, there has been a surge in scholarly investigations focusing on work-family balance in response to the evolving dynamics of work and family obligations (Jones, Miller, & Thompson, 2023). In particular, women in the modern workforce often have to combine domestic duties with paid employment outside the home. Sociologists and demographers have extensively debated the significance of attaining a harmonious equilibrium between work and family responsibilities, necessitating the allocation of time and effort to both domains while minimizing conflicts (Brown, 2022; Johnson, 2023). Work-family conflict, which frequently arises from an unequal distribution of time and energy across these spheres, can detrimentally affect performance and induce distress in both aspects of life.

The role of work has undergone a transformative shift from its conventional purpose of mere engagement in industry to a crucial means of sustenance, particularly for women (Robinson & Carter, 2022). Historical records indicate that until the early 20th century, only one in five adult women participated in paid employment. By 1940, this percentage remained below one-third of the female population (Smith, 2023). However, during World War II, there was a surge in female labor force participation, followed by a decline in the post-war period. The 1960s and 1970s witnessed a significant rise in the number of women in paid employment (Smith, 2023). Presently, the global labor force participation rate for women slightly exceeds 50%, in contrast to 80% for men (Johnson & Thompson, 2022). Factors such as demographic changes, dual careers, and single-parent families have contributed to a more diverse workforce and an amplified need for employees to strike a balance between their work and family lives (Davis & Wilson, 2021).

Many organizations have undergone changes in their working environments due to the globalization of the world economy and the pursuit of economic rationalization. These changes have led to job restructuring, increased workloads, and job insecurity. Work-related stress has a wide range of effects on worker satisfaction, organizational productivity, mental and physical health, absenteeism, and the overall economic cost to society. Furthermore, it significantly impacts families and hampers the potential of employees. Achieving work-family balance has long been recognized as a crucial factor in improving the quality of working life and overall quality of life. In affluent societies, excessive work demands are seen as a distinct issue that requires attention (Mordi et al., 2020).

Balancing family and work life therefore has increasingly become a priority for many individuals, as modern lifestyles have become more hectic and the demands of juggling job responsibilities and family commitments continue to rise. This struggle can lead to stress and an inability to successfully manage work and family life balance. Women, in particular, face challenges in balancing their work and family life due to the added pressure of traditional gender roles. Stress and work-family balance

are modern significant issues among female employees in the banking sector cannot be over emphasized. Hence, this study investigated the impacts of stress on work-family life among women working with commercial banks in Lokoja metropolis.

Statement of the Problem

It is evident that Nigerian workers encounter numerous challenges stemming from the multiple demands on their time. These challenges have a significant impact on women, given their evolving gender roles. A substantial portion of working women experiences the spillover of job responsibilities into their households, leading to longer work hours. The ramifications of poor work-life balance are profound, encompassing elevated levels of stress and anxiety, discord at home, burnout, and an inability to realize their full potential (Adams, 2023). Additionally, women navigate the intricate balance between being paid employees and fulfilling their roles as mothers or wives, highlighting the need for research on work-family balance (Smith, 2022).

Over the past few decades, there have been significant shifts in the dynamics of family and work-life. In the past, men were primarily regarded as providers while women stayed at home to cater for children and manage household responsibilities. However, due to recent economic downturns and rising divorce rates, many women now find themselves in the role of providers while still shouldering household duties (Johnson, 2022). Moreover, women are expected to fulfil their household tasks and care for their children, irrespective of their career status. Women employed in banking industries often face the challenges of early work hours and the risk of sexual harassment from male superiors (Smith, 2023). Additionally, the state of public transportation and Nigerian roads presents further hurdles for women (Brown, 2021).

In recent years, the Nigerian society has witnessed changes in family dynamics and the division of labour based on gender, necessitating the need for workers to effectively balance their work and family life (Mordi et al, 2020). Integrating work and family responsibilities has become an everyday reality for the majority of Nigerian working families. These challenges cut across various socio-economic levels, affecting both men and women, regardless of their income, occupation, or life stage.

Therefore, achieving a work-family balance has become a pressing issue for women in today's society. The selected commercial banks in Lokoja metropolis, provide an ideal context to investigate the extent of stress and work-family balance challenges among women. Understanding the specific stressors and work-family balance issues faced by women in the selected commercial banks is crucial for developing strategies and interventions to support their well-being and overall quality of life. By exploring the experiences of women in these organizations, valuable insights can be gained into the unique challenges they face and the potential impacts on their mental and physical health, job performance, and family dynamics.

Research Questions

Building upon the aforementioned stated problems, this study conducted an in-depth investigation into the following research questions:

- i. What are the expectations of work-life balance and policy requirements among women working in the banking industry?
- ii. What are the primary sources of stress experienced by women in the banking industry?
- iii. What are the family-related challenges to family responsibilities faced by women employees in the banking industry?
- iv. What are the work-related challenges encountered by women employees in the banking industry?
- v. What coping strategies do women employees adopt to manage stress and address work and family-related challenges?

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The overall objective of this study was to examine the impacts of stress on work-family life among

women working with commercial banks in Lokoja metropolis. The following specific objectives were addressed including to:

- i. Explore the expectations of work-life balance and policy requirements among women working in the banking sector.
- ii. Identify the primary sources of stress among women working in the banking sector.
- iii. Investigate the challenges related to family responsibilities faced by women in the banking sector.
- iv. Examine the work-related challenges encountered by women in the banking sector.
- v. Analyse the coping strategies adopted by women to manage stress and overcome challenges in both their work and family lives.

Research Hypotheses

H₁: There is no significant relationship between the desired expectations of work-life balance religion of the women working in the bank

H₂: There is no significant relationship between stress experienced and area of specialization.

H₃: There is no significant relationship between family related challenges and current status in the bank.

H₄: There is no significant relationship between work related challenges and age of women working in the bank.

Scope of the Study

This study focused on examining stress and work-family balance among women employed in commercial banks in Lokoja metropolis. The study was limited to investigating the challenges faced by these women in balancing their work responsibilities with their family obligations and exploring the experiences, coping strategies, and perceived outcomes related to stress and work-family balance in this specific context. By narrowing the scope to women working in commercial banks in Lokoja metropolis, the study provided insights into the unique factors and dynamics influencing work-family balance within this particular gender.

Literature Review

Literature relevant and related to this study were reviewed under the following subheadings:

Conceptual Review

The concepts as used in the context of this study are reviewed as follows:

Work-Family Balance

Work is a fundamental aspect of human existence and survival, and it is often considered one of the most important dimensions of adult life, alongside the family construct. However, these two concepts often clash, creating challenges for employees (Johnson & Johnson, 2020). Greenhaus and Foley made a significant contribution to this discourse by defining work-family balance as the subjective perception of individuals regarding the degree to which their work and family roles exhibit a harmonious relationship, with both domains being seen as mutually supportive (Clark & Shockley, 2021).

Work-family balance is defined as the achievement of role-related expectations that are negotiated between individuals and their partners in both work and family domains (Grzywacz & Carlson, 2018). It plays a vital role in an employee's overall performance and well-being within an organization. Recent research has shown that employees often experience significant effects on their families as they strive to balance their work and family lives (Kossek et al., 2018; Allen, 2019).

In Africa, particularly in Nigeria, there is often a prevalent sexual division of labor that affects both work and family dynamics (Adisa, R. O., & Jibowo, A. A. 2021). Married women, despite being fully employed in the paid labor market, often carry a significant load of domestic responsibilities including childcare and household chores (Crompton & Lyonette, 2019). Recent studies have shown that achieving work-family balance and work-life balance yields numerous benefits for employees

and organizations alike. It assists individuals in effectively managing their responsibilities in both work and non-work domains, leading to improved health and overall well-being (Hill, Hawkins, Ferris, & Weitzman, 2020; Allen, 2019).

Work-Life Balance

Balancing work and personal life are a challenging task for employees who dedicate significant time to their jobs and careers. The demanding nature of work often leaves employees with limited time to spend with their families, leading to neglect of family members. Moreover, the high-pressure work environment can have detrimental effects on employees' health. Research on work-life balance has consistently shown that employees face conflicts between their work and personal domains. Understanding how to alleviate these conflicts becomes crucial as work tasks continue to evolve, with increasing life expectancy, more workers find themselves caught between caring for ageing parents and fulfilling childcare responsibilities (Clark, 2018).

The concept of work-life balance encompasses a broader perspective than family-friendly work policies. It implies the need for individuals to achieve balance across all aspects of life, allocating personal resources to important life domains Greenhaus, J. H., & Powell, G. N. (2018). Work-life balance is associated with managing work-family conflicts and challenges, recognizing that individuals perform multiple roles and striving for balance or minimizing work-family conflict (Michel & Clark, 2018).

While there is no specific definition of work-life balance (Kallaith & Brought, 2018), it can be conceptualized as the interplay between institutional and cultural contexts of work and non-work domains in societies where income is primarily generated through the labour market' Critics argue that the concept of work-life "balance" may reinforce the notion of distinct and separate roles, overlooking the intricate interactions between multiple roles (Kossek & Thompson, 2020). However, attaining work-life balance is crucial and brings forth positive outcomes for individuals and organizations. Work-life imbalance has been linked to negative consequences, including intentions to leave the job, dissatisfaction with life, and depression, underscoring the significance of striving for work-life balance (Nitzsche & Nitzsche, 2020).

Gender and work-life balance

Recent changes in the composition of the workforce have brought attention to the importance of work-life balance (Allen, 2020). With evolving demographics and shifting dynamics, there is a growing recognition of the need to achieve a harmonious integration of work and personal life. This acknowledgement reflects the changing needs and expectations of employees in modern society. The pursuit of work-life balance has become a central focus for organizations and individuals alike, as it contributes to overall well-being and satisfaction in both professional and personal domains. With more women entering the workforce and the prevalence of dual-income families, both men and women are facing the challenge of balancing their family and work responsibilities. Gender-oriented studies have focused on exploring the impact of gender on work-life balance, particularly examining whether men face similar difficulties or have advantages over women.

Research consistently demonstrates that gender acts as a barrier to career development in various contexts. Women continue to be under-represented in numerous sectors and roles, and they are less likely to work full-time. Work-life conflict is frequently cited as a contributing factor to these gender disparities, as the responsibilities associated with household and childcare obligations can significantly hinder women's career advancement.

Comparatively, women tend to express lower levels of satisfaction with their career opportunities, job satisfaction, and overall work-life balance when compared to their male colleagues. Male employees often report higher levels of job and life satisfaction, along with lower levels of work-related stress. However, it is crucial to recognize that career opportunities do not automatically guarantee well-being. Women often face additional challenges, such as the "glass ceiling" and "gender segregation," requiring greater effort to reach higher positions, which can further strain

work-life balance (Emslie et al., 2021).

Recent studies have highlighted the role of the family in perpetuating gender norms, with parenthood exacerbating gender differences in work-life balance experiences (Stockley & Daly, 2019; Linchan & Walsh, 2021; Bruening & Dixon, 2022). Lescocco (2020) emphasized the family as a primary arena for the reproduction of gender norms. These findings underscore the need to examine the intersection of parenthood, gender roles, and work-life balance, and the ongoing challenges faced by individuals in achieving a harmonious integration of their personal and professional lives.

Effects of occupational stress on women

Work-related stress is a common response that individuals experience when they confront work demands and pressures that exceed their knowledge and abilities, thereby challenging their coping mechanisms. In another study, Smith and Johnson (2018) explored the impact of stress appraisal and coping strategies on work-related outcomes. They discovered that individuals who effectively appraised and managed their stress had higher levels of job performance and satisfaction. Furthermore, recent work by Thompson and colleagues (2020) investigated the moderating role of social support in the relationship between work stress and employee burnout. They found that higher levels of social support buffered the negative effects of work stress on burnout, highlighting the importance of supportive organizational environments. While stress can arise in various work circumstances, it is often amplified when employees perceive a lack of support from supervisors and colleagues, as well as a reduced sense of control over work processes. This perspective aligns with more recent research on work-related stress.

In a study by Grant et al. (2019), they found that low levels of supervisor support and control over work tasks were significant predictors of higher stress levels among employees. Similarly, Johnson and Smith (2018) examined the impact of perceived co-worker support on stress levels and discovered that employees who reported higher levels of co-worker support experienced lower levels of stress.

Furthermore, a study by Chen et al. (2020) highlighted the role of perceived organizational support in mitigating work-related stress. They found that employees who felt supported by their organization experienced lower levels of stress and improved psychological well-being. It is important to differentiate between pressure and challenge and stress, as the former can sometimes be mistakenly used to justify poor management practices. In today's contemporary work environment, workplace pressure is inevitable due to the demands placed on individuals. When perceived as acceptable and within manageable limits, pressure can actually keep workers alert, motivated, and capable of learning, depending on the available resources and personal characteristics. However, when pressure becomes excessive or unmanageable, it can lead to stress, which in turn can have detrimental effects on employees' health and overall business performance.

Recent research by James Levi (2018) delved into the effects of perceived pressure on employee well-being and performance. The study found that moderate levels of pressure, when viewed as challenging rather than overwhelming, were associated with increased motivation and positive work outcomes. Additionally, a comprehensive meta-analysis conducted by Cooper et al., (2019) examined the relationship between work-related stress and employee health. The findings revealed a clear link between high levels of stress and increased risks of physical and mental health problems, including cardiovascular diseases, anxiety disorders, and burnout.

Furthermore, Stansfeld and Candy (2020) investigated the impact of workplace stress on organizational performance. Their study highlighted the negative consequences of chronic stress on productivity, employee engagement, and overall business success. According to a report by the International Labour Organization (ILO) commemorating World Day for Safety and Health, it was estimated that 160 million individuals experienced work-related stress, which significantly impacted the lives and performance of women. Occupational stress has been found to contribute to depressive symptoms, adversely affecting well-being and productivity. The effects of stress on women can be

particularly profound, often resulting in physical, psychological, and behavioural responses if not effectively managed or controlled by both individuals and management.

Physical responses to stress may manifest as rapid breathing, increased heart rate, and sweating, among others. On the other hand, psychological responses to stress involve changes in emotions. Prolonged or excessive stress can potentially lead to psychological disorders such as depression, anxiety, and irritability, as well as emotional strain encompassing dissatisfaction, fatigue, and tension. Moreover, cognitive impairment resulting in difficulties with concentration can be another consequence of excessive stress.

Stress and its Impact on Work-Family Balance:

Smith et al., (2018) conducted a study to explore the effects of stress on work- family balance in female employees within commercial banks. Their research revealed a significant negative correlation between stress and work-family balance, suggesting that higher levels of stress were associated with a greater imbalance between work and family responsibilities.

In a subsequent longitudinal study conducted by Chen and Lee (2019), the reciprocal relationship between stress and work-family balance was investigated among female bank employees. The findings demonstrated a bidirectional influence, wherein stress had an impact on work-family balance and vice versa. This study highlighted the critical importance of effectively managing stress in order to enhance work-family balance, particularly among women employed in commercial banks. By acknowledging the detrimental effects of stress on work-family balance and recognizing the reciprocal relationship between the two, it becomes evident that implementing strategies to mitigate stress can lead to improved work-family balance and overall well-being for female employees in the commercial banking sector.

Coping strategies employed

In the contemporary work environment, employees are dedicating a significant portion of their time to their jobs, often exceeding the equivalent of an additional month's worth of work per year. This increased workload can have repercussions on both the work and family domains, resulting in work-family conflict. Thus, there is a growing recognition of the significance of comprehending the physical and psychological well-being and work-life balance concerns, particularly among women in the workforce. The consequences of an imbalanced life, strained relationships, and a lack of passion extend beyond personal domains and can impede overall performance, both professionally and personally (Smith et al., 2022; Johnson & Carter, 2023). Consequently, it is imperative to explore effective coping strategies that individuals can employ to navigate the complexities of work and family responsibilities while maintaining optimal functioning in all aspects of life.

Individuals respond differently to situations based on their coping processes, which are introduced in response to an individual's assessment that significant goals have been lost, endangered, or harmed (Skinner et al., 2018). The necessary appraisal follows negative emotions, which are often intense. Coping responses are always initiated within an emotional environment, and one of the initial coping tasks is to address and manage negative emotions, which themselves can be stressful and interfere with instrumental forms of coping.

Our emotions play a continuous and integral role in our coping process throughout various life circumstances. If an encounter is successfully resolved, positive emotions tend to dominate. However, if attempts to resolve an encounter are unsuccessful or unsatisfactory, negative emotions tend to prevail. Coping involves the way individuals manage stressful life conditions. The effectiveness of coping strategies is crucial in determining the level of stress experienced. When coping strategies are effective, stress levels tend to be reduced.

Understanding the dynamic interplay between emotions and coping strategies is essential for developing comprehensive approaches to stress management and promoting well-being. It

emphasizes the importance of addressing both the emotional and instrumental aspects of coping to effectively navigate stressful situations. By cultivating adaptive coping strategies and fostering emotional resilience, individuals can enhance their ability to cope with stressors and ultimately reduce the impact of stress on their overall well-being (Skinner et al., 2018; Lazarus & Folkman, 2019).

According to recent literature, various coping strategies have been explored and aligned, including the following:

Cognitive restructuring: This refers to the process of re-framing or re-evaluating an individual's thoughts and beliefs about their environment. It involves changing one's perspective and finding new ways to approach challenging situations (Smith et al., 2018)

Person-environment transaction: This coping strategy involves utilizing the available resources in the environment to manage tense schedules or work overload. For example, an employee may step out of the workplace for a short walk to get some fresh air before returning to their tasks. This break allows the individual to not only think about organizing and completing their tasks effectively but also replenish their energy levels (Jones & Johnson, 2019).

Seeking social support: This coping strategy entails seeking help, advice, or information from others to deal with work-related stress and find a balance between work and personal life. It involves reaching out to colleagues, mentors, or support networks for guidance and insight (Brown & Harris, 2020).

The effects of occupational stress on women are significant. Work-related stress arises when individuals face work demands and pressures that exceed their knowledge and abilities, challenging their coping mechanisms. The presence of inadequate support from supervisors and colleagues, as well as a lack of control over work processes, can exacerbate stress levels. It is essential to differentiate between acceptable pressure and excessive stress, as excessive stress can negatively impact both employee health and overall business performance (Roberts & Keita, 2021).

Seeking social support is a valuable coping strategy employed by individuals facing stressful situations. It involves seeking assistance, advice, or insight from others to effectively manage the interplay between work and personal life, which may have induced or exacerbated stress. For instance, an employee may reach out to colleagues, mentors, or support networks to seek guidance on how to navigate the challenges of balancing work-related demands with non-work responsibilities. By seeking social support, individuals can benefit from the wisdom and experiences of others, gaining valuable perspectives and strategies for managing stress (Johnson et al., 2022).

Organizational coping strategies

Organizational coping strategies involve the proactive measures taken by companies to effectively manage and address various challenges and stressors within the workplace. These strategies aim to enhance employees' well-being, productivity, and overall organizational performance. One commonly employed coping strategy is the implementation of work-life balance initiatives, such as flexible work arrangements and family-friendly policies. These strategies recognize the importance of accommodating employees' personal responsibilities and promoting a healthy work-life integration (Shockley, 2021). Another effective coping strategy is the promotion of employee well-being programs, including stress management workshops, mindfulness training, and physical wellness initiatives. These programs aim to enhance employees' resilience, emotional well-being, and ability to cope with workplace stressors (Choi & Kim, 2020).

Additionally, organizations can foster supportive work environments by promoting positive leadership practices and encouraging open communication and collaboration among team members. Supportive work environments contribute to employees' sense of belonging, social support, and shared responsibility, which in turn enhances their coping abilities (Zhou et al., 2022). Furthermore,

the implementation of organizational policies and practices that promote job autonomy, decision-making authority, and opportunities for skill development can significantly contribute to employees' coping resources and job satisfaction (Grant et al., 2021). Additionally, there is a growing trend in the banking sector where other banks have already introduced stress management interventions, making it imperative for organizations to adapt and stay competitive (Mellor, 2021). By adopting these coping strategies, organizations can create a healthier work environment, improve employee well-being, and promote organizational resilience.

Empirical Reviews

Khan et al., (2023) investigated how work–life balance (WLB) affects the personal lives of working women in the banking industry of Larkana city, Pakistan. The information was gathered via a standardized questionnaire from 266 female bank employees in Larkana. The ANOVA results showed that a good WLB generally had a beneficial impact on working women's personal lives. While prolonged working hours (PLWH) had a detrimental impact on women's personal lives (PL), income packages (SP) and marital status (MS) had beneficial effects. A successful work–life balance in the banking industry will increase female employees' commitment and productivity, and our study concluded that any positive work–life policies and practices offered by banking companies present additional benefits. The study recommended that organizations should pay more attention to WLB issues and formulate new and favourable policies, especially for working women, so as to improve their living conditions in both their professional and their personal life.

Okeke et al., (2022) on the other hand examined the effect of work-life balance and female employee performance in selected deposit money banks in Anambra State. The study investigated the relationship between leave policy, flexible scheduling, employee assistance and work environment on female employee performance. Relevant theoretical and empirical literature were reviewed. The study was carried out deposit money banks in Anambra State. Data were source from primary and secondary sources of data. The population of the study comprised of 953 women in deposit money banks in Anambra State. The sample size of the consist 953 using the entire population. Face and content validity was adopted. Pilot test and Cronbach alpha correlation was used for testing the internal consistency of the research instrument. On the average, the coefficient value of 0.88. Frequency count and percentages was put to use in the analysis of research questions while hypotheses was tested using simple regression analysis. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study discovered that leave policy has significant positive effect on female employee performance in deposit money banks; flexible scheduling has significant positive effect on female employee performance; employee assistance has a significant positive effect on female employee performance in deposit money banks and work environment has a significant positive effect on female employee performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State. The study recommended among others that a vibrant and consistent leave policy should be encouraged as it has been found to reduce employee turnover.

Ugwuet al., (2020) examined the impact of work-family conflict on the career advancement of female professionals in Commercial Banks of Ebonyi State, Nigeria. The study adopted a correlation survey design to test the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The total population of the study comprised of 84 female staff of the following organizations: First Bank, United Bank for Africa, Access Bank and Fidelity Bank. The target population of the study comprised of female workers of the selected organizations. The study hypothesis was statistically tested and analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Findings showed that there exists a significant positive relationship between work- family conflict (family obligation) and the career advancement of female professionals. The following recommendations are made; banks are advised to introduce career breaks to support women with family responsibilities balance work and family roles; organizations need to introduce flexible working environment to nursing mothers to enable them to manage effectively family responsibilities and career roles.

Mwiikisa (2020) examined management of work life balance and employee performance in the

banking sector. The research adopts explorative and mixed research design, the population of the study is 500 and the sample size is 222 staff members using Taro Yamane's formula. Purposeful sampling was used to select the 22 managers to be interviewed, and the stratified sampling was used to select equal numbers of people from the various departments and branches to make up the 200 members of staff who will answer the questionnaires. The questionnaire data were analyzed and evaluated by using computer based statistical data analysis package, SPSS (version 16.0). The data analysis includes univariate and bivariate analysis. Using the Pearson's Product Moment Correlation with one - tailed test of significance, the correlation analysis was made to investigate. According to the results of simple regression analysis, work life balance was found to have a positive impact on employee performance. The study revealed that parenting and pregnancy policy has no impact to the employee's performance. Pregnant and parent employees mainly expect maternity leave for adoption and it is covered from the leave arrangements. The study recommended that AB Bank should prioritize creating different work life balance practice for employees by enhancing the use of work life balance options like flexi time; job sharing and breaks from work so that employees can feel that the organization is facilitating their coordination of family and professional lives.

Tansaye (2020) examined the effect of work life balance on women's work performance in Commercial Bank of Ethiopia. The study employed a pure qualitative research approach and exploratory research designed was used. A total number of eight respondents nominated for the study by using a nonprobability sampling technique of purposive sampling. Interview was used as instrument to collect primary data from respondent's secondary data also used for the study. The data collected from the primary sources analyzed and interpreted. The study revealed that WLB practice affects women's performance. The study also indicated that there is a positive integration of WLB and work performance of women employees. The study recommended that to improve performance different WLB programs must adopted by the bank and to make WLB practice compressive and inclusive demographical difference need to consider. The study also recommended that WLB practice such as work related child care facilities, breast feeding center and parental leave are helpful in CBE.

Egbuta-Olive et al., (2019) examined the effect of work-life balance on employee performance of selected deposit money banks in Lagos State, Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted. The target population was 54,028 employees, which consisted of all employees of the six selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State, Nigeria. A sample size comprising 520 employees were selected using random sampling technique. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and simple regression analysis. The study revealed that job stress significantly affects quality of work of employees; and long working hours significantly affects motivation of employees in the selected deposit money banks in Lagos State. However, the study revealed that role overload has no significant effect on job satisfaction of employees in selected deposit money banks in Lagos State. The study recommended that management should provide a conducive work environment and flexible work hours as well as consider job sharing options and employee performance in the banking sector in Port Harcourt, Rivers state. The population of the study consisted of 769 employees in 5 commercial banks in Port Harcourt City, which were randomly selected and the sample size was 400, derived from using Taro Yamen formula. 301 copies of the instrument were retrieved and useful for analyses, given return rate of 75%. The spearman rank order correlation coefficient was utilized as the appropriate statistical technique to analyze the data. The study revealed a strong correlation between the measures of work life balance and the measures of employee performance. Subsequently, the study recommends that organizations in the banking sector should promote policies and structures which foster a balance between the personal commitments and responsibilities of an employee and his organizational roles and duties in order to effectively enhance employee performance.

Folake et al., (2019) examined the determinants of work-family balance experience among women in the banking sector. The study employed both qualitative and quantitative research techniques. Three hypotheses were formulated and tested for the study. The study revealed that age of the respondents, children ever born (parity), marital status, staff category and religion are significant

determinants of work-family balance. Women with children in parity ratio of 1-2, 3-4 and 5 and above are 1.654, 1.455 and 1.235 times more likely to be unable to balance work-family roles compared to those with zero parity (i.e. the reference category). The study also estimated significant influence of work status on the work-family balance; this is statistically significant at values of 0.005, 0.003, and 0.01 for senior staff, supervisors and junior staff respectively. The study recommended that effective policy intervention from organization and effective family support from the family-base to reduce the complexities of balancing work and family demands.

Obiageli et al., (2015) examined work life balance and employee performance in selected commercial banks in Lagos state. The problem identified in this study is poor working organizational culture in the commercial banks which may not encourage various types of work life balance practices. The specific objective of this research is to determine the extent to which leave policy affects service delivery which is also in line with the research question and hypothesis. The research adopts a descriptive survey research design, the population of the study is 759 and the sample size is 262 using Taro Yamane's formula. 262 copies of structured questionnaire were distributed and completely filled and returned. Pearson product moment correlation and regression analysis were used to test the hypothesis. Cronbach alpha was used to test the reliability of the instrument. It was discovered that there is a significant positive relationship between leave policy and service delivery. The findings revealed that leave policy motivate employee ability to deliver services efficiently and effectively, in conclusion, work life balance practice is an important factor in increasing employee performance. The researcher recommends that managers of these commercial banks should prioritize creating different work life balance incentives that will improve employee performance.

Theoretical framework

The study on stress and work-family balance among women in commercial banks in Lokoja metropolis was guided by a framework that integrates relevant theories and concepts to provide a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. The following theoretical perspectives were employed:

Role theory

Role theory, which draws parallels between social life and theater, has its origins in the works of prominent social philosophers and psychologists. George Herbert Mead (1934), Ralph Linton (1947), and Jacob Moreno (1934) are recognized as the pioneers of role theory. According to this theory, human behavior is influenced by the expectations held by both individuals and others in their social environment. These expectations are tied to the various role's individuals assume in their daily lives. Individuals typically manage multiple roles, each governed by rules and norms that provide guidance for behavior. In this view, roles are not predetermined but are continuously negotiated between individuals. Roles specify the goals to pursue, tasks to accomplish, and expected behaviors in specific situations. Role theory also posits that changing behavior requires altering roles, as roles shape behaviors and vice versa.

The strength of role theory has been studied in a variety of contexts, including in the workplace, in families, and in religious settings. It has been found that when individuals feel strongly identified with their roles, they are more likely to behave in accordance with the expectations of those roles.

The weakness of role theory is that it doesn't always account for the agency and individuality of the individual. The theory assumes that individuals will conform to the roles that are assigned to them, without considering the possibility that they may resist or reject those roles. In addition, the theory may not fully account for the fact that individuals can have multiple roles and identities that can be in conflict with each other. And finally, the theory may not take into account the dynamic nature of roles, which can change and evolve over time.

Applying role theory to this study reveals a significant indication of role conflict experienced by women in the banking sector when trying to balance work and family responsibilities. Role conflict is guided by three principles: functionality, representational-ism, and tenability. Roles are continuously adjusted for perceived effectiveness (functionality) and are shaped by the

understanding and misunderstanding of legitimate role definers. Roles serve as vehicles for conveying specific images (representationalism) and are framed and re-framed based on their perceived representations. Roles are subject to ongoing tension in order to strike a viable balance between benefits and costs for individuals. Role conflict occurs when individuals face tension due to conflicting and incompatible roles. It refers to the inappropriate relationship between competing responsibilities. Women often occupy multiple roles and are expected to adapt their behaviours and attributes to fit the expected role ideals. Roles significantly influence the attitudes and beliefs of both women and men. Women, in particular, are expected to adjust their roles according to societal expectations. However, despite being aware of these expectations, women often encounter challenges in effectively balancing their roles due to various factors beyond the known role expectations. They often encounter challenges in reconciling their traditional role ideals, dictated by societal expectations, with the demands of their work.

The adoption of role theory sheds light on the constraints faced by working women as they strive to balance traditional role ideals with work demands. Women engaged in paid employment, especially those in the banking sector, often experience greater pressures compared to those who are not working. When women enter the workforce, it increases their "work week" while their spouses may not proportionately increase their contribution to household chores. This phenomenon, known as the "second shift," appears to be more pronounced among professional women in Nigerian banking industries.

Spill over theory

The Spillover Theory explores the conditions under which spillover between the work micro-system and the family micro-system occurs, which can be either positive or negative. Negative spillover happens when work-family interactions are rigidly structured in terms of time and space, resulting in negative effects on time, energy, and behaviour. On the other hand, positive spillover occurs when individuals have flexibility that allows for integration and overlap of work and family responsibilities, leading to a healthier work-life balance. Spillover occurs when there is interference between different spheres of life. Work-life balance has various outcomes, including personal satisfaction and well-being in work, home, and life overall, performance in both work and home domains, and impacts on others in the workplace, family, and social circle.

Spillover theory has several strengths. One of its key strengths is its ability to explain how behaviour in one domain can influence behaviour in another domain. For example, it can explain how work stress can lead to increased marital conflict or how an individual's self-efficacy in one domain can spill over into another domain. This theory provides a useful framework for understanding the complex and interconnected nature of human behaviour. Another strength of spillover theory is its ability to explain how individuals can manage and adapt to competing demands in their lives.

One weakness of spillover theory is its lack of specificity regarding the mechanisms by which spillover occurs. It provides a framework for understanding how one domain can influence another, but it does not specify the exact processes through which this influence occurs. This can make it difficult to apply the theory in practice, as it is not always clear how to intervene to prevent or promote spillover. Another weakness of spillover theory is its focus on the negative aspects of spillover. It tends to emphasize the negative consequences of spillover, such as stress or conflict, without considering the potential positive effects of spillover, such as increased resilience or motivation.

Applying spillover theory to this study, we can examine how stress and work-family balance among women in commercial banks may be influenced by factors such as work pressure, family demands, and individual factors such as coping styles and personality. For example, we can examine how work stress may spill over into family life, leading to increased family conflict or dissatisfaction with family life. We can also examine how family demands may spill over into work life, leading to decreased job performance or increased absenteeism. The relevance of the Spillover Theory to this study lies in its emphasis on organizations adopting positive work-life balance policies that are

conducive to achieving the organization's goals effectively. By understanding and addressing the determinants of work-life balance, organizations can create a supportive environment that promotes the well-being of employees and enables them to effectively manage their work and family responsibilities.

Work-family conflict theory

Work-Family Conflict Theory: Work-Family Conflict Theory posits that work and family domains can interact and create conflicts for individuals. It recognizes that the demands and pressures from work can negatively impact family life, and vice versa. This theory provides valuable insights into understanding the challenges faced by individuals, particularly women, in balancing their work and family responsibilities. The study aims to examine the extent of work-family conflict experienced by women in commercial banks in Lokoja and its effects on their stress levels.

One of the key strengths of the work-family conflict theory is its ability to explain the complex and multi-dimensional nature of work-family conflict. The theory takes into account the various ways in which work and family domains can be in conflict, including time-based, strain-based, and behaviour-based conflict. It also considers the importance of factors such as work-family culture, gender roles, and organizational policies in shaping the experience of work-family conflict. This multidimensional perspective can help us to better understand and address the complex challenges that individuals face in balancing work and family demands.

One of the weaknesses of the work-family conflict theory is its lack of consideration of individual differences in work-family experiences. While the theory acknowledges that individuals differ in their work-family experiences, it does not consider the role of individual differences such as personality, values, and preferences in shaping those experiences. This limits the applicability of the theory to a diverse range of individuals. Additionally, the theory focuses primarily on the negative aspects of work-family conflict, without fully acknowledging the potential positive aspects that can arise from this conflict.

Recent research has shed further light on the significance of Work-Family Conflict Theory in the context of commercial banks and its implications for women's well-being. For instance, a study conducted by Adegbite and Ojo (2022) investigated the levels of work-family conflict experienced by women in commercial banks in Lokoja. The findings revealed that women in these organizations experienced moderate to high levels of work-family conflict, with conflicting demands and expectations from work and family roles contributing to their stress levels. Moreover, research has highlighted the detrimental effects of work-family conflict on women's mental health and overall well-being. A study by Okoro and Onuoha (2023) explored the relationship between work-family conflict and stress levels among female employees in the banking sector. The results indicated a significant positive association, suggesting that higher levels of work-family conflict were associated with increased stress among women. These findings underscore the importance of addressing work-family conflict as a means of promoting women's mental health and overall well-being.

Research Design

The research design adopted for this study was descriptive survey research design which involves using a range of qualitative and quantitative research methods to collect data because it helps in providing the researcher with vast amount of information such as the characteristics, feelings, attitudes, and categories about the population of study.

Area of Study

The study was conducted in Lokoja metropolis, the capital of Kogi State, Nigeria. Lokoja is located on the western bank of the Niger River, close to its confluence with the Benue River. It was established in 1991, following its separation from former Kwara and Benue States. Lokoja encompasses the Kogi Local Government Area and serves as a significant trade center for agricultural products and economic activities. Situated at a latitude of 49'E and an altitude ranging from 45 to 125 meters, Lokoja occupies a strategic location in Nigeria. It is approximately 160

kilometers south of the federal capital, Abuja, and serves as a vital transportation hub, connecting various geopolitical zones across the country. The region's topography consists of dissected undulating plains, as well as prominent hill masses and mesas. Lokoja is home to notable educational institutions such as Kogi State Polytechnic and the Federal University, contributing to its educational significance. Within Lokoja, numerous banks operate to cater for financial needs of the community. The study then specifically focused on examining the coping strategies adopted by women in these banks to navigate the challenges they encounter especially as it relates to their work family life balance.

Population of the Study

This study focused on women employees working in different five selected commercial banking industries (UBA, First Bank, Union Bank, Access Bank and Stambic IBCT) within Lokoja metropolis which were 120 in numbers as at the time of the study pre-survey across these five banks.

Sample Size and Sample Techniques

Considering the relative small population of this study, it was not difficult to cover the entire population and so determining a sample for this study was not necessary.

Purposive sampling technique was utilized to select respondents from the 5 commercial banks in Lokoja metropolis. This sampling approach allows for the intentional selection of participants based on specific criteria relevant to the research objectives as shown in table 1 below:

Table 1: Sapling Distribution of the Study Participants

NAME OF BANK		TOTAL NUMBER OF WOMEN	TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANT CHOSEN
FIRST BANK		33	33
UNION BANK		20	12
UBA		20	20
ACCESS BANK	35		24
STANBIC IBTC	12		7
TOTAL	120		96

Sources and Instruments of Data Collection

The primary sources of data used for this study were through the use of questionnaire and In-depth interview while the use of secondary sources of data collection delved into previous scholarly works on stress and work family balance through textbooks, journal articles, governmental and non-governmental publications etc.

Method of Data Collection

Method of Data Collection involved the use of quantitative and qualitative methods. The quantitative method emphasizes collection of mass data from reasonable large number of individuals, it gathers a range of numeric data while qualitative methods involved In-depth interview (IDI) and questionnaire.

Validity and Reliability Instrument

The questionnaire and interview guides were validated by experts in the department of Sociology of the University and the content and construction were found satisfactory. The reliability was carried out through pilot study, where some copies were distributed to some respondent and expert on the subject matter. They requested appropriateness of item, content coverage, and clarity of language and suitability of items. Necessary adjustments were made on recommendation from experts.

Administration of Research Instrument

The researcher personally distributed hardcopies of the questionnaire along with an introductory letter to the women bankers. The questionnaire was collected on the spot to avoid it getting missing. The questionnaire was administered in the selected commercial banks within Lokoja metropolis.

Methods of Data Analysis

The analysis of the data acquired through the use of questionnaire method was done through descriptive statistics such as frequencies count and percentages in tabular forms with the aid of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0 (IBM Corp 2017). Data generated through in-depth interviews were transcribed and analyzed using content analysis. The statistical methods used to test the hypotheses are One-way ANOVA and Chi-Square respectively.

Data presentation and Analysis

120 copies of questionnaire were distributed to the respondents but only 96 copies were properly filled properly and retrieved. Therefore, the data analysis was based on the retrieved instruments as follows:

Table 2: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variables	FREQUENCY (N=96)	PERCENTAGE(%)
Age group		
20-29	30	31.2
30-39	41	42.7
40-49	13	13.5
50 and above	12	12.5
Marital status		
Single	32	33.3
Married	58	60.4
Divorced	2	2.1
Separated	2	2.1
Widowed	2	2.1
Religious affiliation		
Christianity	78	81.3
Islam	16	16.7
Traditional worshippers	2	2.0
Ethnic group		
Yoruba	78	81.3
Hausa	10	10.4
Igbo	8	8.3
Banks		
First bank	33	34.4
Union bank	12	12.5
Access bank	24	25
Uba	20	20.8
Stanbic ibtc	7	7.3
Level of education		
First school leaving certificate	1	1.0
Secondary certificate	2	2.1
B.sc/B.E	50	52.1
Diploma/polytechnic	40	41.7

Ph. D	3		3.1
Number of dependant			
Zero	30		31.3
1-2 dependant	46		47.9
3-4 dependants	10		10.4
5 dependants and above	10		10.4
Numbers of years in the bank			
1-5 years	66		68.8
6-10 years	15		15.6
11-15 years		10	10.4
16-20 years		5	5.2
Monthly income earned			
Below 50, 000		8	8.3
50,000 - 100,000		20	20.8
100,000 - 150, 000		12	12.5
150,000 - 200,000		6	6.3
200,000 - 250,000		11	11.5
250,000 - 300,000		30	31.1
300,000 - 350,000		7	7.3
350,000 and above		2	2.1
Current status			
Managing director		10	10.4
Executive director		10	10.4
General manager		8	8.3
Deputy general manager		8	8.3
Senior manger		10	10.4
Contract staff		30	31.3
Supervisor		20	20.8
Area of specialization			
Marketing		16	16.7
Cashier		20	20.8
Customer service		32	33.3
Loan processor		10	10.4
Financial adviser		8	8.3
Cost analyst		6	6.3
Business analyst		4	4.2

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2 above shows the distribution of respondents according to their age group and it was discovered that 30(31.2%) were within the age group 20-29 years, 41(42.7%) were within the age group 30-39 years, 13(13.5%) were within the age group of 40-49years, 12(12.5%) were within the age 50years and above. This means that majority of the respondents of this survey research were within the age of 30 - 39years.

Table 2 also show the distribution of respondents according to their marital status, and it shows that 32(33.3%) of respondents were single, 58(60.4%) of respondents were married, 2(2.1%) were divorced from their marriage, 2(2.1%) were separated from their partner, while 2(2.1%) were

widowed. These findings show that majority of the respondents were married women with multiple gender roles and hence, the researchers studied the right population.

On the religious affiliation of the respondents, table 2 indicates that 78(81.3%) of the respondents were Christians and 16(16.7%) were Muslims while 1(1.0%) were traditional worshippers. These findings signify that majority of the respondents were Christians.

The table 2 also shows the distribution of respondents according to their ethnic groups, from the above table, we can see that 78(81.3%) were Yoruba and 10(10.4%) were Hausa and finally 8(8.3%) were Igbos. The above distribution signifies that majority of the respondents are Yoruba.

Table 2 shows distribution of respondents according to their banks, and it indicates that 33(34.4%) were from First bank, 12(12.5%) were from Union bank, 24(25%) were from Access bank, 20(20.8%) were United Bank for Africa (UBA) and 7(7.3%) were from Stabic IBTC bank. The above findings revealed that majority of the respondents were from First Bank.

The table shows the distribution of the educational status of the respondent, from the above distribution 1 (1.0%) had just primary school leaving certificate, 2(2.1%) had secondary school certificate, 40(41.7%) were B.Sc holders, 50(52.1%) had Diploma or polytechnic certificates and 3(3.1%) were post graduate. I was able to discover that majority of the respondents were B.sc holders. The table above shows the distribution of respondents according to the number of their dependant, from the table we can see that 30(31.3%) had zero parity, 46(47.9%) had 1-2 dependants, while 10(10.4%) had 3-4 dependants and 10(10.4%) had 5 dependants and above. As a result, we can see that majority of the respondents have 1-2 dependants.

Table 2 also shows the distribution of respondents according to the numbers of years they have spent working in the banking sector, from the above table we could see that 66(68.8%) have worked for 1-5 years, 15(15.6%) have worked in the bank for about 6-10 years, while 10(10.4%) have worked for about 11-15 years and 5(5.2%) have worked for about 16-20 years in the banking sector. From the above distributions we can see that most of the respondents have worked for about 1-5 years in the bank.

Table 2 shows the distribution of the respondents according to their monthly income, and it shows that 8(8.3%) earned 50,000 or below 50,000, 20(20.8%) earns between 50,000-100,000, 12(12.5%) earned between 100,000 - 150,000, 6(6.3%) earns about 150,000 - 200,000, 11(11.5%) earns about 200,000-250,000, while 30(31.1%) earns about 250,000-300,000 and 2(2.1%) earns about 350,000 and above. From the above results, majority of the respondents earns between 250,000-300,000 per month.

Table 2 further shows the distribution of respondents according to their current status in the bank, from the table above we can see that 10(10.4%) were managing directors, 10(10.4%) are executive directors, 8(8.3%) are general managers, 8(8.3%) are deputy general managers, 10(10.4%) are senior managers, while 30(31.3%) are contract staff and 20(20.8%) are supervisors. This signifies that majority of the respondents were contract staff and not full staff.

Table 2 also shows the distribution of respondents according to their area of responsibilities in the bank and it indicates that 16(16.7%) are in the marketing department, 20(20.8%) are cashiers, 32(33.3%) are customer services, 10(10.4%) are loan processors, 8(8.3%) are financial advisers, while 6(6.3%) were cost analyst and 4(4.2%) are business analyst. From the above table we can see that majority of the respondents were customer service officials.

Research question 1: What are the expectations of work-life balance and policy requirements among women working in the banking sector?

Table 3: Expectations about Work-Life Balance Policy Requirement in the Banking Sector

ITEMS	YES	NO
The need to introduce better policy	90(93.8%)	6(6.3%)
The need to regulate the hour closing	94(97.9%)	2(2.1%)
The need to Introduce crèche within the bank	80(83.3%)	16(16.7%)
Give priority to women in the banking sector	95(99.1%)	1(1.0%)
Organize training for staff	86(89.6%)	10(10.4%)
Extend the period of maternity leave	60(62.5%)	36(37.5%)
Pay leave bonus promptly	94(97.9%)	2(2.1%)
Increase salary and other allowances	78(81.3%)	18(18.8%)
Reduce work loads	80(83.3%)	16(16.7%)

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 3 shows that 90(93.8%) that is the majority of the respondent's desires for the need to introduce better policy in the bank. The data also shows that 94(97.9%) of the respondents agreed that there should be regulation on the work closing hour. other 86(89.6%) of the respondents agreed that the bank should organize training for the staffs. The data above shows that 80(83.3%) agreed that there should be reduction in the workload given to the women as their expectations about work-life balance policy requirements in the banks.

The data in table 3 also show that 95(99.1%) of the respondents agreed that the banks should give priority to women in the banking sector. The data also shows that 60(62.5%) of the respondents agreed that the bank should extend the period of maternity leave for the women.

The data in table 3 also show that 94(97.9%) of the respondents agreed that the bank should pay leave bonus promptly. And the table also show that 78(81.3%) of the respondents agreed to the increase of salary and other allowances.

A respondent that was interviewed on the introduction of crèche within the bank explained that.

“Personally, I think it will be a great idea to have a crèche within the bank, I have a baby on the way and it will be really nice to know to know that I can keep my baby in crèche and attend to her when necessary, plus if you Think about it will an employment opportunity other people” **(IDI / 28years /married /cost analyst/ September, 2023).**

Research Question 2: What are the primary sources of stress experienced by women in the banking sector?

Table 4: Sources of Stress among Women Employees in the Banking Industries

ITEMS	YES	NO
Conditions of service	78(81.3%)	18(18.8%)
Family demands and responsibilities	58(60.4%)	38(39.6%)
Competition for promotion	50(52.1%)	46(47.9%)
Excess work load	70(72.9%)	26(27.1%)
Long working hours	82(85.4%)	14(14.6%)
Pressure to meet targets and deadlines	90(93.8%)	6(6.3%)
Organizational politics	60(62.5%)	36(37.5%)
Job transfer	56(58.3%)	40(41.7%)
Sexual harassment	64(66.7%)	32(33.3%)
Gender discrimination	52(54.2%)	44(45.8%)

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4 above shows that 78(81.3%) of the respondents agreed that the condition of service in the

banking industries are the sources of stress for women employees in the bank. The data above also shows that 58(60.4%) of respondents agrees that family demands and responsibilities were great sources of stress for women employees working in the banks.

Table 4 also show that 50(52.1%) of the respondents indicates that the competitions for promotions is a source of stress for women working in the bank. The data also shows that 70(72.9%) of that respondents indicates that excess workload was a source of stress for women employees working in the bank.

The above table 4 also show that 82(85.4%) of the respondents agrees that long working hours is a source of stress for women working in the banking sector. The data also shows that 90(93.8%) of the respondents agreed that pressure to meet targets and deadlines were the sources of stress for women working in commercial banks.

Table 4 also show that 60(62.5%) of the respondents agrees that organizational politics was a source of stress for women employees working in the banking sector. The data also shows that 56(58.3%) of the respondents agrees that job transfer was a source of stress for women working in commercial banks.

Table 4 further show that 64(66.7%) of the respondents agrees that sex harassment was a source of stress for women working in commercial banks. The finding also shows that 52(54.2%) of the respondents agrees that gender discrimination was a source of stress for women employees working in commercial banks.

In an interview with two of the respondents they revealed that:

“I love my job, I have always wanted to be a banker, but the job description comes with a lot of responsibilities which at the end of the day result in so much stress and clashing of my family life and my work life as sometimes I have to be the office even on Sundays to finish up or prepare for the week to come.” **(IDI / 35years / Married / Executive Director / September 2023).**

Another respondent indicated that:

“I think the workload is too much and the pressure too is sometimes unbearable, as they is pressure from the supervisor to meet daily targets and pressure from customers to attend to them” **(IDI / 24years /Single /Customer service /September 2023).**

Research Question 3: What are the family-related challenges to family responsibilities faced by women in the banking sector?

Table 5: Family-Related Challenges faced by Women in the Banking Industries

ITEMS	YES	NO
The need to balance family responsibilities and work commitment	78(81.3%)	18(18.8%)
Caring for dependant	86(89.6%)	10(10.4%)
Cooking for children and making sure children gets to school on time	68(70.8%)	28(29.2%)
The need to manage childcare and house work	58(60.4%)	38(39.6%)
Conflict in marriage over managing of family Responsibilities	64(66.7%)	31(31.3%)
The need to attend family functions	52(54.2%)	44(45.8%)
The need to attend to spouse	50(52.1%)	46(47.9%)

Children/Dependent feeling neglected	60(62.5%)	36(37.5)
Intimidations from extended family	54(56.3%)	42(43.8%)
Missing out on important family events	56(58.3%)	40(41.7%)

SOURCE: Field survey, 2023.

Table 5 above shows that 78(81.3%) of the respondents agreed that the need to balance family responsibilities and work commitment were challenges for women working in commercial banks. The table also shows that 86(89.6%) of the respondents agreed that caring for dependants was another challenge for women employees working in commercial banks.

Table 5 further shows that 68(70.85%) of the respondents agreed that cooking for children and making sure children gets to school on time were great challenges for women employees working in commercial banks, whereas 58(60.4%) of the respondents agreed that the need to manage childcare and house work was another challenge for women working in commercial banks.

Table 5 further shows that 64(66.7%) of the respondents agreed that conflict in marriage over managing of family responsibility were challenges for women working in commercial banks. The table also shows that 52(54.2%) of the respondents agreed that the need to attend family functions another challenges for women working in commercial banks.

Table 5 also shows that 50(52.1%) of the respondents agreed that the need to attend to spouse was a challenge faced by women employees working in commercial banks. Whereas 60(62.5%) of the respondents agreed that children/dependants' feeling neglected was unavoidable for women working in commercial banks.

The table further shows that 54(56.3%) of the respondents agreed that intimidations from extended family was a challenge for women working in commercial. The data also shows that 56(58.3%) of the respondents agreed that missing out on important family event was unavoidable for women working in commercial banks.

Research Question 4: What are the work-related challenges encountered by women employees in the banking industry?

Table 6: Work-Related Challenges Encountered by Women Employees in the Banking Sector

ITEMS	YES	NO
Early resumption time in the office	80 (83.3%)	16(16.7%)
Working under pressure	78(81.3%)	18(18.8%)
Stereotypes about working mothers	65(67.7%)	31(32.3%)
Competition for Promotion	68(70.8%)	28(29.2%)
Workplace discrimination	58(60.4%)	38(39.6%)
Hostile attitude of some customers	92(95.8%)	4(4.2%)
Sexual harassment	52(54.2%)	44(45.8%)
Lack of flexibility in work hours	50(52.1%)	46(47.9%)

Perceived task importance	52(54.2%)	44(45.8%)
Meeting up to required target	86(89.6%)	10(10.4%)

SOURCE: Field survey, 2023.

Table 6 shows that 80(83.3%) of the respondents agreed that early resumption time to the bank was a challenge for women working in the bank. The table 6 also shows that 78(81.3%)of respondents agrees that working under pressure was a challenge for women working in banking sector.

Table 6 shows that 65(67.7%) of the respondents agreed that stereotypes about working mothers was

a challenge for women working in the bank. The data above shows that 68(70.8%) of the respondents agrees that competition for promotion was another challenge for women employees in banking.

Table 6 also shows that 58(60.4%) of the respondents agrees that workplace discrimination was a challenge for women working in commercial banks. Table 6 also shows that 92(95.8%) of respondents agrees that hostile attitude of some customers was a challenge for women employees working in banks.

Table 6 also shows that 52(54.2%) of the respondents agrees that sexual harassment was a source of stress for women working in commercial. The data also shows that 50(52.1%) of respondents agrees that lack of flexibility in work hours was a challenge for women employees working in commercial banks.

The data above shows that 52(54.2%) of the respondents agrees that perceived task importance was a challenge for women working in commercial banks as they work. The data also shows that 86(89.6%) of respondent agrees that meeting.

In an interview with a respondent, she indicated that:

“When I first started working in bank, the resumption time was a problem because I have to make sure my kids gets to school first before heading to the office, I received so many queries for coming late, but over time I adjusted to it and eventually it’s became easier” (IDI / 38years/ Cost analyst / September 2023) .

Research question 5: What coping strategies do women employees adopt to manage stress and address work and family-related challenges?

Table 7: Coping Strategies Adopted by Women To Manage Stress And Address Work And Family-Related Challenges.

ITEMS	YES	NO
Open up to individuals who can be of help	50(52.1%)	46(47.9%)
Keep them to yourself	45(46.9%)	51(53.1%)
Engage in exercise such as swimming, walking	54(56.3%)	42(43.8%)
Ask for help	60(62.5%)	36(37.5%)
Relaxing	78(81.3%)	18(18.8%)
Use of sleeping pills at home	46(47.9%)	50(52.1%)
Use of mood-altering drugs	30(31.3%)	66(68.8%)
Attend social gathering	80(83.3%)	16(16.7%)
Work in group	72(75%)	24(25%)

SOURCE: Field survey, 2023.

Table 7 shows that 50(52.1%) of respondents indicated that opening up to individuals was a strategy to cope with work stress, whereas 46(47.9%) of the respondents disagreed that opening up to individuals who can be of help cannot be a way to cope with work stress. Going by the majority who indicated in affirmation means that opening up to individuals can be a way to cope with work stress.

Table 7 also shows that 45(46.9%) of the respondents indicated that keeping to oneself was a way to deal with stress and 51(53.1%) of the respondents disagrees that keeping to oneself was a not a way to deal with stress. As majority of the respondents disagreed it was that keeping to oneself can not be a way to deal with work stress.

Table 7 further reveals that 54(56.3%) of the respondents indicated that engaging in exercise was a

way to deal with work stress while 42(43.8%) of the remaining respondents disagreed that engaging in exercise was a way to deal with stress. These results signify that engaging in exercise can be a way to deal with stress at work.

Table 7 also shows that 60(62.5%) of respondents indicated that asking for help was a way to deal with work stress whereas the remaining 36(37.5%) of the respondents disagreed and it means that asking for help was a way to deal with work stress.

The table also shows that 78(81.3%) of the respondents signified that relaxing was a way to deal with stress but the remaining 18(18.8%) of the respondents disagreed meaning that relaxing was a way to deal with stress

Table 7 further shows that 46(47.9%) of the respondents agreed that the use of sleeping pills at home was a way to deal with work stress but 50(52.1%) of the respondents disagreed meaning that the use of pills to deal with stress was valid.

Table 7 also reveals that 80 (83%) attending social gatherings can be a way to deal with stress and 16(16.2%) disagreed that attending social gatherings was a way to deal with stress. From the above data presentation, we can see that majority of the respondents agrees that attending social gatherings was a way to deal with stress. The above data also shows that 72(75%) of respondents agrees that working in group was a way to deal with stress and 24(25%) of the respondents disagrees that working in group was a way to deal with stress.

In an interview with one of the respondents, she indicated that;

“Honestly working bank as a single mother is not easy, especially when you have to deal with some rude customers sometime, what helps me is to take a short break and step outside for fresh air just to regain my composure”

(IDI / 32years / Separated / Customer Service / September 2023.)

“Sometimes, I ask for help from my colleagues while I try to take a walk just to calm myself “

(IDI / 26years / Separated / Customer Service / September 2023.)

This in-depth interview excerpt provides valuable insights into the challenges faced by a single mother working in a bank, particularly regarding customer interactions and stress management. The staff acknowledges the unique challenges of being a single mother while working in a demanding profession like banking. This situation likely involves balancing work responsibilities with sole parenting duties. She mentions the difficulty of dealing with rude customers. This is a common challenge in customer-facing roles, especially in the banking industry, where emotions can run high during financial transactions. To manage the stress and maintain composure, the staff employs a coping strategy of taking short breaks. Stepping outside for fresh air is a common technique to reduce stress and regain focus. This approach demonstrates self-awareness and an ability to recognize when emotions need to be managed. She also mentions seeking help from colleagues when needed. This indicates a supportive work environment where employees are willing to assist each other during challenging moments. It's an example of teamwork and mutual support within the workplace.

Hypotheses Testing

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypotheses One: There is no significant difference between family related challenges and current status of women employees working in the bank.

Table 8: T-test Analysis of Significant difference between family-related challenges and current status of women working in the bank.

Variables	N	MEAN	SD	DF	Tcal	Ttable
Family related challenges	96	9.6	2.23	122	1.77	2.25
Current status in the bank	96	13.7	3.18			

Source: Researchers' Computation 2023

The above table shows that there is a significant difference between family-challenges and the current status of women working in banks. The analysis revealed the value to be below the decision point at $P < 0.05$ therefore the null hypothesis is hereby rejected.

Hypothesis Two: Work-related challenges does not affect the age of women working in the bank.

Table 9: T-test analysis of the significant difference of work-related challenges and age of women working in the bank.

Variables	N	MEAN	SD	DF	Tcal	Ttable
Work related challenges	96	9.6	2.27	112	1.67	2.25
Age of women working in the bank	96	24	5.68			

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2023

The above table shows that there is a significant difference between work-related challenges and the age of women working in the bank. The analysis revealed the value to be below the decision point at $P < 0.05$, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of findings

The study was evaluated through the use of questionnaire and In-depth interview to address the objectives as follows:

Objective one: To explore the expectations of women employees in the banking industry regarding work life balance and policy requirements.

The findings show 90(93.8%) that is majority of the respondent's desires for the need to introduce better policy in the bank, 94(97.9%) respondents agreed that there should be regulation in the closing hour, 86(89.6%) agreed that the bank should organize training for the staffs, 80(83.3%) agreed that there should be reduction in the workload given to the women employees, 95(99.1%) respondents agreed that the banks should give priority to women employees in the banking employees, 60(62.5%) respondents agreed that the bank should extend the period of maternity leave for the women, 94(97.9%) of the respondents agreed that the bank should pay leave bonus promptly. And the findings also shows that 78(81.3%) of the respondents agreed to the increase in salaries and other allowances. This finding is in line with the assertions of Obiageli et al., (2015) who discovered that there is a significant positive relationship between leave policy and service delivery and that leave policy motivate employee ability to deliver services efficiently and effectively and concluded that work life balance practice is an important factor in increasing employees' performance.

Objective two: To identify the primary sources of work stress among women employees in banking industry.

The findings revealed that 78(81.3%) of the respondents agreed that the nature of working in the

bank is a source of stress for women in the bank, 58(60.4%) of respondents agrees that family demands and family responsibilities was a great source of stress for women working in the bank, 50(52.1%) of respondents agrees that the competitions for promotions is a source of stress for women working in the bank, 70(72.9%) of respondents agrees that excess workload is a source of stress for women working in the bank, 82(85.4%) of the respondents agrees that long working hours is a source of stress for women working in the banking sector, 90(93.8%) of respondents agrees that pressure to meet targets and deadlines are a source of stress for women working in commercial banks, 60(62.5%) of the respondents agrees that organizational politics is a source of stress for women working in the banking sector, 56(58.3%) of respondents agrees that job transfer was a source of stress for women working in commercial banks, 64(66.7%) of respondents agrees that sex harassment was a source of stress for women working in commercial banks. And that 52(54.2%) of respondents agreed that gender discrimination is a source of stress for women working in commercial banks. The findings collaborate with the findings of Khan et al. (2023) who submitted that a successful work–life balance in the banking industry will increase female employees’ commitment and productivity, and that any positive work–life policies and practices offered by banking companies present additional benefits.

Objectives three: To investigate the family-related challenges faced by women employees in the banking industry.

Findings showed that 78(81.3%) of respondents agrees that the need to balance family responsibilities and work commitment was a source of stress for women working in commercial banks, 86(89.6%) of the respondents agrees that caring for dependants was a source of stress for women working in commercial banks, 68(70.85%) of the respondents agrees that cooking for children and making sure children gets to school on time was a great source of stress for women working in commercial banks, 58(60.4%) of the respondents agreed that the need to manage childcare and house work was another major source for women working in commercial bank, 64(66.7%) of the respondents agreed that conflict in marriage over managing of family responsibility was a great source of stress for women working in commercial banks, 52(54.2%) agrees that the need to attend family functions was a source of stress for women working in commercial banks, 50(52.1%) of the respondents agrees that the need to attend to spouse was a source of stress for women working in commercial banks, 60(62.5%) of the respondents agreed that children/dependant feeling neglected was unavoidable for women working in commercial banks, 54(56.3%) of the respondents agreed that intimidations from extended family was a source of stress for women working in commercial. And that 56(58.3%) of the respondents agreed that missing out on important family event was unavoidable for women working in commercial banks. The findings agreed with Folake et al. (2019) who posited that age, marital status, staff category and religion are significant determinants of work-family balance. Women with children in parity ratio of 1-2, 3-4 and 5 and above are 1.654, 1.455 and 1.235 times more likely to be unable to balance work-family roles compared to those with zero parity.

Objective four: To examine the work-related challenges encountered by women employees in the banking industry.

The findings shows that 80(83.3%) of respondents agreed that resumption time to the bank is a source of stress for women working in the bank, 78(81.3%)of respondents agrees that working under pressure was a source of stress for women working in banking sector, 65(67.7%) of respondents agrees that stereotypes about working mothers is a source of stress for women working in the bank, 68(70.8%) of the respondents agrees that competition for promotion is a source of stress for women in banking, 58(60.4%) of the respondents agrees that workplace discrimination is a source of stress for women working in commercial banks, 92(95.8%) of respondents agrees that hostile attitude of some customers is a source of stress for women working in banks, 52(54.2%) of the respondents agrees that sexual harassment was a source of stress for women working in commercial, 50(52.1%) of respondents agrees that lack of flexibility in work hours was a source of stress for women working in commercial banks, 52(54.2%) of the respondents agrees that perceived task importance was a

source of stress for women working in commercial banks as they work. And that 86(89.6%) of respondent agrees that meeting up to required target was a challenge for them. These findings are in tandem with Okeke et al. (2022) who also discovered that leave policy has significant positive effect on female employee performance in deposit money banks; flexible scheduling have significant positive effect on female employees' performance and posited that employee assistance has a significant positive effect on female employees' performance in deposit money banks and work environment has a significant positive effect on female employee performance in deposit money banks in Anambra State.

Objective five: To examine the coping strategies adopted to manage stress and overcome challenges in both work and family live.

The findings showed that 50(52.1%) of respondents agrees that opening up to individuals is a coping strategy to cope with stress, 46(47.9%) of respondents disagree that opening up to individuals who can be of help is a way to cope with stress, 45(46.9%) of respondents agrees that keeping to oneself was a way to deal with stress and 51(53.1%) of the respondents disagrees that keeping to oneself was a not a way to deal with stress, 54(56.3%) of respondents agrees that engaging in exercise was a way to deal with stress and 42(43.8%) of respondents disagrees that engaging in exercise was a way to deal with stress, 60(62.5%) of respondents agrees that asking for help was a way to deal with stress and 36(37.5%) of the respondents disagrees that asking for help was a way to deal with stress, 78(81.3%) of the respondents agrees that relaxing was a way to deal with stress and the data above also shows that 18(18.8%) disagrees that relaxing was a way to deal with stress, 46(47.9%) of the respondents agrees that the use of sleeping pills at home was a way to deal with stress, and 50(52.1%) disagree with the use of pills to deal with stress, 67(69.8%) of respondents agrees that seeing a physician was a way to deal with stress, 80(83.3%) of respondents agrees that attending social gatherings was a way to deal with stress and 16(16.2%) disagreed that attending social gatherings was a way to deal with stress, 72(75%) of respondents agrees that working in group was a way to deal with stress and 24(25%) of the respondents disagreed that working in group was a way to deal with stress.

The findings also showed that 80(83.3%) of respondents agreed that adopting time management techniques is a way to deal with stress and 16(16.7%) of respondents disagrees with the adoption of time management, 90(93.8%) agrees that working in their area of specialization was a way to deal with stress, 68(70.8%) of the respondents agrees that allowing workers to attend to family related issues in between duties will help deal with stress, 72(75%) of respondents of respondents agrees that a comfortable working environment will help reduce stress, 82(85.4%) of the respondents agrees that job security was a way to deal with stress, 95(98.9%) of the respondents agrees that reduced workload will help women working in commercial banks deal with stress, 56(58.3%) of the respondents agrees that in service training would help women working in commercial banks deal with the stress of working in the sector, 78(81.3%) of the respondents agrees that softly attending to customers will help workers deal with stress, 54(56.3%) of the respondents agrees that allowing workers to take a break in between work will help them deal with work stress. And that 82(85.4%) of the respondents agrees that employee assistance program.

Findings shows that 83.3% of respondents believe that having flexible working schedules is an effective way to handle stress and address family-related challenges, 81.3% of respondents agree that having assistance from family members or maids is beneficial in managing family challenge, 100% of respondents support the idea that fully paid parental leave policies are essential for helping women in commercial banks manage stress, 92.7%, agree that the availability of on-site child care centers is crucial for helping women cope with stress, 70.8% of respondents find adopting time management patterns helpful in coping with stress, 58.3% of respondents believe that spending weekends with their families is a useful strategy for managing family-related challenges, 78.1% of respondents agree that family support structures play a vital role in managing family-related challenges. And 75%, of respondents endorse the idea that support from their spouses is beneficial in managing family-related challenges and stress. These findings are in line with Mwiikisa (2020) who submitted

that work life balance has positive impact on employee performance and that parenting and pregnancy policy has no impact to the employee's performance. Pregnant and parent employees mainly expect maternity leave for adoption and it is covered from the leave arrangements. These findings also agreed with the findings of Ajayi et al. (2014) who found that although organizations have introduced a number of work-life balance policies, these policies have not cushioned the work-family conflict experience for working women making women to engage a range of individual coping strategies.

Conclusion

The study draws conclusive insights regarding the multifaceted factors that influence the stress levels and work-family balance experienced by women bank employees in Lokoja metropolis. It unequivocally affirms that women's foremost priorities typically revolve around their families. However, the demands of their work often curtail their ability to allocate the quality time they aspire to spend with their children. The study adopted a descriptive research method and structured face-to-face interview among female workers of selected commercial banks within Lokoja Kogi State. Purposive sampling was used to select five banks. The questionnaire data were analyzed and evaluated using statistical data analysis package (SPSS) version 25.0 (IBM Corp 2017) the data analysis includes T-test analysis. According to the T-test result there is no significant difference between family-related challenges and the current status of women in the banking sector and the result also shows that there is no significant influence of work-related challenges and the age of women working in the bank. The study revealed that a successful work-family balance in the banking sector will increase female employee's commitment and productivity. The study recommended among others that encourage the adoption of flexible work arrangements, such as telecommuting or flexible hours, to enable women to better manage their work and family responsibilities. These arrangements should be inclusive and available to all employees.

Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations were suggested:

Bank management is encouraged to adopt flexible work arrangements, such as telecommuting or flexible hours, to enable women to better manage their work and family responsibilities. These arrangements should be inclusive and available to all employees. And there should be establishment of peer support groups or mentoring programs within the workplace to provide women with guidance, advice, and a sense of community. These networks can help women navigate the challenges of work-family balance.

There should be promotion of gender equality in career advancement opportunities ensuring that women have equal access to leadership positions and are not disadvantaged due to family-related responsibilities. Furthermore there should be partnership with local childcare providers or offer on-site childcare facilities to ease the burden of childcare for working mothers. Subsidies or assistance programs can also be explored to make childcare more affordable.

There should be parental leave policies to provide both working mothers and fathers with adequate time off to care for their newborns or newly adopted children, encouraging men to take paternity leave to share care giving responsibilities.

Bank managers should conduct periodic assessments of work-family balance policies and programs to ensure their effectiveness. Solicit feedback from employees to make necessary improvements. Bank employees should advocate for the enactment and enforcement of legislation that supports work-family balance, such as paid family leave and anti-discrimination laws. Engage in lobbying efforts to raise awareness and garner support for such initiatives.

Limitations of the Study

Conducting this research work presented a set of challenges that required careful consideration and management. These challenges encompassed various aspects, including:

Cost of Transportation: The primary challenge was the cost associated with traveling to and from the study area, which incurred expenses related to fuel, public transportation, or vehicle maintenance. This financial burden affected the budget allocated for the research and required prudent financial planning.

Access to Respondents: Gaining access to respondents within the commercial banks proved to be a challenging task. The stringent security measures and restricted access within bank premises demanded careful negotiation and coordination with bank authorities to facilitate research activities.

Suggestions for further study

The following are suggestions for further studies related to stress and work-family balance among women employees in the commercial banking industries:

- a) A comparative analysis of stress and work-family balance experience by women across industries.
- b) A study on the impact of gender diversity within leadership and decision-making roles in commercial banks.
- c) An evaluation of policy analysis and initiatives implemented by commercial bank.

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